

ANALYSIS OF DIRECT AND INDIRECT ASSESSMENTS IN GENERAL BOTANY AND ZOOLOGY: INPUT FOR PEDAGOGICAL IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Commission on Higher Education is committed to developing and implementing an outcomes-based approach to QA monitoring and evaluation because it has the potential to dramatically boost both the effectiveness of the QA system and the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of higher education. The results are the focus of mature evaluation systems, which look at the intended, implemented, and achieved learning outcome. As a result, faculty members in all science courses conduct direct and indirect assessments of course outcomes. Hence, in-depth analysis of these assessments was done in this study which sole purpose is to introduce improvements in instructions and assessments which can generally be called pedagogy. To meaningfully delve into the breath of this research, mixed methodology was used, with the results of the direct and indirect assessments being administered to students taking General Botany and Zoology and supported by the documentary analysis, interview, and focus group discussion. The perception of the students on the course outcomes as shown in the result of indirect assessment may serve as predictor of their performance in the direct assessment being given to them both in lecture and laboratory. The explorations of the direct and indirect assessments revealed that both assessments are based on OBE-CQI and related CHED issuance. Relative to the purpose they are used as concrete evidence of quantifiable students' performance. More so, they were also found to be relevant to teaching and learning processes while, it was also revealed that the common tools and instruments used by teachers' examination, performance task, laboratory activities, and survey form. The implications drawn from the analysis of direct and indirect assessments include the need to boost the interest, attitude, aptitude of the students in a particular lesson as it influences the performance of students in lecture, and in the conduct of laboratory activities. A lesson guide that addresses issues and concerns on the students' perceptions about the course outcomes as revealed in the indirect assessments and the results of direct assessments was prototyped which geared towards pedagogical improvement.

Keywords: Analysis, Direct and Indirect Assessment, Mixed Method